

A Case Study of Korean Cultural Education Using K-Content

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Article Info

Article History

Received:
July 15, 2024

Accepted:
October 16, 2024

Keywords :

K-Content, Hallyu,
Culture Education,
K-MOOC

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.13941757

Abstract

The demand for Korean language education as a foreign language has been steadily increasing, resulting in a growing number of Korean language programs worldwide. Recognizing the importance of integrating cultural education into language instruction, efforts have been made to enhance the teaching of Korean culture. However, existing programs often lack comprehensive content and fail to provide a holistic understanding of Korean culture. To address this gap, our research team developed a Korean Massive Open Online Course (K-MOOC) titled "Learning Korean Culture through K-Content." This course utilized a variety of K-content, including movies, dramas, literature, and K-pop, to teach Korean culture. A detailed course description, along with the results of a course satisfaction survey, is presented. The survey results indicated high satisfaction in all categories, including course content, the effect of using K-content, overall satisfaction, and post-course changes. Participants found the course valuable for both learning the Korean language and gaining a deeper understanding of Korean culture. This study underscores the significance of cultural education in language learning and offers insights for developing effective programs. It also lays the foundation for shaping the future of cultural education for international students at universities.

Introduction

Universities in South Korea (hereafter referred to as Korea) are witnessing a steady increase in the number of international students at the tertiary level. This growth can be attributed to various factors, including Korea's rising global status, improved educational standards, and the influence of the Korean Wave (Hallyu). According to 2021 statistics from the Korean Ministry of Education, the number of international students enrolled in higher education institutions has been increasing by nearly 20,000 annually since 2016, prior to the COVID-19 pandemic. In 2020, the total number of international students reached 153,695, marking a 12.8% rise in degree-seeking students compared to the previous year (Ministry of Education, 2021). The increase in the number of international students reflects the growing international interest in Korea. Additionally, a 2021 study by Wang and Pyun highlights the global popularity of Korean popular culture. The study shows that in the past decade, Korean language enrolment in U.S. higher education institutions has grown more than that of any other foreign language.

The history of Korean language education as a foreign language dates back quite some time, and recently, there has been a growing emphasis on integrating Korean cultural education into Korean language instruction. In response, Korean universities are striving to diversify their Korean language education programs, particularly those aimed at international students. As part of these efforts, our research team—comprising experts in Korean language and literature, graphic design, Vietnamese, and English education—developed and delivered a Korean Massive Open Online Course (K-MOOC) that incorporates Korean cultural content (hereafter K-content) to teach students about Korean culture. The objective of the present study is to introduce the K-MOOC course developed by our research team as a model for integrating cultural content, and to share the results of a satisfaction survey conducted among students who participated in the 15-week course.

Literature Review

Most international students at Korean universities learn Korean by taking elective Korean language courses. Achieving a certain level of Korean language proficiency is essential for adapting to life in Korea and succeeding in their major studies, making Korean language education a crucial part of their learning process. However, numerous studies have highlighted that a sole focus on language proficiency in Korean language education can lead to limitations in improving international students' communication skills (Choi & Chae, 2010; Eom, 2012; Han, 2010; Kim, 2005; Kim, 2011; Kwon, 2013; Park, 2008; Park, 2009). This is because mastering the language alone may not be sufficient for students to engage in in-depth conversations, exchange information

effectively, or fully explore their academic fields. Kim (2005), for example, argued that “learning a language means to contact not only the words but also the culture” (p. 69), suggesting that language and culture should be taught in tandem. In her case, she emphasized the importance of reading literature, through which learners can acquire both linguistic knowledge and an understanding of the target culture.

Popular culture has long been used, whether “consciously or unconsciously,” in foreign language teaching, as learners are exposed to a large amount of pop culture in foreign languages through mass media (Zeng & Yung, 2022, p. 415). However, as Zeng and Yung noted in their review of Werner and Tegge’s edited volume on using pop culture in language education, “the vast inherent potential of pop culture for foreign language education has been underused and underresearched” (Werner & Tegge, 2022, p. 3). The central theme of their book underscores the importance of integrating pop culture into language instruction to motivate learners and enhance their learning experience.

In their analysis of the impact of K-pop culture on schoolchildren in Indonesia, Bahagia et al. (2022) described K-pop as “a very trending culture” (p. 5315) and observed that “the outbreak of the Korean fever epidemic among students in Indonesia has sparked interest in learning foreign languages,” potentially expanding students’ job prospects (p. 5313).

Another important factor to consider is the role of social media. In recent years, social media has played a pivotal role in the spread of pop culture (Zeng & Yung, 2022), with K-pop culture being widely disseminated through these platforms (Bahagia et al., 2022). Given this context, Werner and Tegge (2022) highlighted the need for further research on the use of pop culture in teaching and learning languages beyond English. In line with these trends, Korean language education for international students is increasingly moving away from language-focused instruction and toward the integration of Korean culture into language teaching. This shift towards emphasizing Korean culture in language education at universities has gained significant momentum since the 2010s.

However, Korean cultural education has a relatively limited scope, often relying on fragmented use of literary genres such as novels, poems, and folktales (Ko, 2020; Lee, 2012; Yang, 2006; Yang, 2008; Yang, 2009; Zheng & Jin, 2017). These Korean language courses often fall short of providing a comprehensive understanding of the diverse aspects of Korean culture. To address this, universities should incorporate a broader range of engaging Korean cultural content that aligns with students’ interests. This approach would enable students to gain a deeper understanding of various cultural contexts and explore their academic disciplines more thoroughly.

The present study, therefore, introduces a Korean cultural education course developed as a model for international students, utilizing a MOOC platform. MOOCs are large-scale online courses offered via web-based platforms, allowing unlimited enrolment and open access to anyone interested. Originally initiated in 2011 through collaborations among top universities such as Stanford, MIT, Harvard, and Princeton, MOOCs have since gained widespread popularity across Europe and Asia. Prominent MOOC platforms include FutureLearn in the UK, Iversity in Germany, FUN in France, XuetangX in China, and J-MOOC in Japan (Lee, Kim, & Yang, 2015). Following this global trend, Korea launched its own platform, K-MOOC, in 2015. Initially offering 27 courses from 10 domestic universities, K-MOOC has continued to evolve. As of 2023, it now offers a wide range of courses from over 170 universities and institutions (Ministry of Education, 2023).

One of the key advantages of K-MOOC is that learners can access university-level lectures on a wide range of topics for free. As a result, the number of course registrants has steadily increased, reaching a cumulative total of 2.81 million by 2022. To meet the evolving needs of learners and adapt to the societal changes brought about by the digital transformation era, the South Korean Ministry of Education annually solicits and selects new courses to support the development and implementation of K-MOOCs. In response to the growing global popularity of K-pop and the expanding influence of hallyu, courses focusing on topics such as Korean history, art, and tourism have been actively promoted. The proposal for “Learning Korean Culture through K-Content,” the subject of this study, was accepted and developed as a new K-MOOC course in the field of Korean studies in 2021.

“Learning Korean Culture through K-Content” is a course designed to teach Korean culture through K-content on a MOOC platform. The course aims to make Korean culture easily accessible not only to international students in Korea but also to individuals of various nationalities around the world, allowing them to learn about Korean culture anytime, anywhere. Understanding Korean culture not only contributes to a deeper understanding of Korea but also enhances Korean language proficiency. The following section will provide a detailed overview of the course, followed by an explanation of the survey conducted to explore students’ perceptions of using K-content in their language and cultural learning.

The Study

Course Description: Learning Korean Culture through K-Content

Korean cultural education courses have traditionally focused on language instruction or introduced only limited aspects of Korean culture. This approach has been criticized for offering a narrow understanding of Korea's unique and contemporary characteristics, as well as for lacking engagement and appeal. In contrast, this course adopts a more practical and experiential approach by utilizing a variety of visual and audio-visual cultural content. The term "K-content," as used in this course, refers to a wide range of content that incorporates both traditional and modern elements of Korean culture, serving to express or symbolize Korea as a whole. The content includes genres such as Korean dramas, movies, variety shows, popular music, literature, and folklore, most of which are familiar to foreigners through social media and video streaming platforms. By engaging with these forms of media, learners can explore unfamiliar aspects of Korean culture while gaining a broader and more accessible understanding of Korean culture in general.

This course was first launched in October 2021 and was entering its third year as of 2023. It runs for a total of 15 weeks, including 13 weeks of classes, with midterm and final exam periods excluded. Each week consists of three 25-minute lessons. The course is organized into seven major areas, each further divided into three to six subcategories. By incorporating K-content aligned with the theme of each lecture, the course offers a comprehensive understanding of various aspects of Korean culture. The themes covered include Hangeul and the Korean language, Korean consciousness, Korean popular arts and literature, Korean heritage, traditional living and modern lifestyle, and Korean play culture.

Details of Course Content

Among the seven categorized areas of Korean culture, the first topic is "Hangeul (the Korean alphabet) and the Korean Language." This section covers essential knowledge about the Korean language, including the historical background and principles behind the creation of Hangeul, Korean fonts, idioms, and proverbs. The course also explores contemporary shifts in the Korean language, such as slang, abbreviations, and Konglish. Through media like the drama *Deep-rooted Tree*, which highlights the spirit and scientific principles behind Hangeul's creation, and the film *MALMOE*, which portrays the efforts to preserve Hangeul during the Japanese colonial period, students gain an appreciation for the beauty, scientific nature, and historical significance of Hangeul. Additionally, programs like *Incredible Saturday* offer an engaging way for students to expand their knowledge of various Korean language expressions.

The second topic is "Korean Consciousness." In this section, students explore themes such as life and death, associated rituals and ceremonies, traditional values like loyalty and filial piety, family structures and relationships, major holidays such as Chuseok (Korean Thanksgiving) and Seollal (Korean Lunar New Year), as well as the communal consciousness and religious beliefs of Koreans. Films like *The Festival*, which examines Korean society's views on death, and *The Admiral: Roaring Currents*, which highlights Korean patriotism, provide deeper insights into these cultural aspects. Additionally, students learn about Korean families, holidays, and religion through dramas such as *My Unfamiliar Family* and films like *The Birth of a Family*, as well as through news programs and documentaries.

The third topic involves an in-depth exploration of "Korean Popular Arts," which have gained global recognition. This section covers internationally acclaimed Korean films such as *Parasite*, dramas like *Guardian: The Lonely and Great God*, and the global influence of K-pop, particularly through groups like BTS. It also extends to other forms of artistic expression, including painting, dance, cartoons, and webtoons. The lessons in this category encourage students to reflect on why Korean arts have achieved international recognition and to understand both the uniqueness and the universal appeal of Korean arts that captivate global audiences. Through this topic, foreign students not only enjoy Korean popular arts but also gain a deeper understanding of Korea.

The fourth topic addresses "Traditional and Contemporary Korean Literature," which provides a deeper understanding of the essence of Korean history and life. Students are introduced to representative classical novels and renowned poems, exploring how Korean society has transformed through its literature. This process is vital for developing a more profound understanding of Korean culture and society. The fifth topic focuses on Korea's historical heritage, covering national holidays, cultural landmarks, currency, tourist attractions, and festivals. Teaching materials include films such as *The Battle: Roar to Victory*, which portrays resistance during the Japanese colonial period, the drama *Love in the Moonlight*, set against the backdrop of cultural heritage, and variety programs like *1 Night 2 Days*, which introduces Korean currency. These resources help students explore Korea's historical and cultural legacy in an engaging way.

The sixth topic examines "Traditional and Modern Korean Lifestyles". In the case of traditional lifestyles, students study hanbok (traditional Korean clothing), traditional Korean cuisine, and hanok (traditional Korean houses). Teaching materials include cultural programs like "Korean Table" and popular entertainment programs like *Youn's Kitchen*, as well as advertisements and YouTube videos. To understand modern lifestyles, students explore Korea's advanced IT sector, renowned as one of the best in the world, which provides insight into contemporary Korean daily life.

The seventh and final topic is "Korean Play Culture." This section examines how traditional Korean games have been preserved and transformed into modern games or revived as elements of popular arts. It also explores how Korean play culture has evolved into globally popular content through entertainment programs. Shows like *Running Man* and *I Live Alone* help students explore Korean leisure culture and understand how Koreans balance their busy modern lives.

The Survey

A total of 150 students were enrolled in the course, including 107 foreign students residing in Korea or other countries such as Myanmar, China, Thailand, Japan, Indonesia, and Uzbekistan. The remaining 43 students were Korean. Of the 107 foreign students, 45 participated in the survey, with 13 male and 32 female respondents. Thirty-nine of the respondents were in their 20s, followed by four in their 30s, and two in their teens. The nationality breakdown of the respondents is as follows.

Table 1. Participants

Nationality	No.
China	22
Myanmar	12
Thailand	5
Uzbekistan	3
Vietnam	3
Total	45

Of the 107 foreign students, 29 were exchange students taking the course for credit, while the remaining 78 were international students who enrolled voluntarily out of personal interest.

To assess satisfaction with the use of K-content in teaching Korean culture and to gain valuable insights for future content development, this study conducted a survey targeting foreign students enrolled in the course "Learning Korean Culture through K-Content." The survey participants were students who took the course from September 2022 to December 2022. The survey questions focused on the course content, the learning effectiveness of K-content, overall satisfaction with the learning experience, and post-class changes. A total of 22 questions were included, and satisfaction levels for each item were measured on a 5-point scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

First, to assess students' satisfaction with the course content, the survey included questions about the level of interest in the organization of the course, the use of K-content, and the level of understanding of the material. Regarding the effect of using K-content, the survey also addressed its impact on students' understanding of the course content, as well as their learning of the Korean language and culture. The overall satisfaction with the course was evaluated as well. Additionally, participants were asked to compare their levels of interest in K-content, Korean culture and language, Korea itself, and their understanding of Korea before and after taking the course.

The survey was provided in both Korean and English using Google Forms, with the link shared on the K-MOOC platform's Learning Korean Culture through K-Content bulletin board. It was conducted from November 30th to December 15th, 2022. The survey clearly outlined the purpose and objectives of the research, and participants were assured that their responses would remain anonymous. Descriptive statistics were calculated to analyze the students' responses to the survey questions. The survey findings will be briefly summarized, followed by a discussion of their implications.

Survey Results

Overall, participants in this study expressed satisfaction with the course content and organization, noting that it helped them improve their Korean language skills and deepen their understanding of Korean culture. Additionally, their responses indicated that the course heightened their interest in Korean culture, boosting their motivation to pursue further courses in Korean language and culture in the future. The survey results will be presented in the following categories: course content, learning effects of using K-content, overall course satisfaction, and post-course changes in perceptions.

Course Contents

The analysis of participants' survey responses reveals a high level of satisfaction with the overall course content ($M = 4.49$, $SD = 0.693$). Participants also found the organization of the course content engaging, with a mean rating of 4.58 out of 5. The K-content used in the course received a rating of 4.60 for its level of interest.

The Effect of Using K-Content

The analysis of participants' responses suggests that the use of K-content had a generally positive impact on their learning experience. Specifically, participants reported that K-content helped them gain more knowledge and experience of Korean culture ($M = 4.62$, $SD = 0.614$), better understand the course content ($M = 4.44$, $SD = 0.725$), and improve their Korean language skills ($M = 4.36$, $SD = 0.883$).

Course Satisfaction

Overall satisfaction with the course was high, with a mean rating of 4.52 ($SD = 0.613$). Participants indicated that the knowledge gained from the course significantly helped them learn both the Korean language and culture. Additionally, responses to the question of whether they would recommend the course to other learners were positive, with a mean rating of 4.58 ($SD = 0.657$).

Post-Course Changes in Perceptions

The survey results indicate an increase in participants' interest in K-content ($M = 4.42$, $SD = 0.723$) as well as in Korean culture and language courses ($M = 4.58$, $SD = 0.657$). Participants also reported a better understanding of Korea after completing the course ($M = 4.71$, $SD = 0.589$). These findings are significant, suggesting that the course led to positive changes in participants' perceptions.

Discussion

The course had a total of 150 students, including 107 foreign students from Myanmar, China, Thailand, Japan, Indonesia, and Uzbekistan, either residing in Korea or in their home countries. Of the 107 foreign students, only 29 were exchange students who took the course for academic credits, while the remaining 78 enrolled voluntarily out of personal interest. This highlights the strong appeal of K-content to foreigners interested in Korean culture, as well as its ability to motivate them to learn. These findings support the notion that K-content can be a valuable tool for teaching Korean culture and language to foreigners (Bahagia et al., 2022; Kim, 2005; Werner & Tegge, 2022).

The satisfaction survey on the use of K-content in learning Korean culture revealed high satisfaction across all categories: course content, the impact of K-content on learning, overall learning satisfaction, and post-course changes. Notably, K-content enhanced students' understanding of Korean literature, history, and popular culture, while providing deeper knowledge and experience of Korean culture and improving comprehension of the course material. Additionally, it increased motivation to learn Korean and contributed to improving language proficiency. After completing the course, participants reported heightened interest in K-content, Korean culture, the Korean language, and Korea itself. The use of K-content also positively influenced Korea's image and helped learners gain a better understanding of the country. These results are significant, demonstrating positive perceptual changes among students after taking the course.

Until recently, Korean cultural education has been limited in scope and insufficient in providing comprehensive coverage of the various aspects of Korean culture (Ko, 2020; Lee, 2012; Yang, 2006; Yang, 2008; Yang, 2009; Zheng & Jin, 2017). However, the course developed by our research team sought to address these limitations. By incorporating diverse K-content aligned with foreign learners' interests—such as the global popularity of K-pop and the rise of the Hallyu wave—and delivering it through a MOOC platform, the course enabled both foreign exchange students in Korea and learners from various countries worldwide to easily access and learn about Korean culture. The significance of this course should not be underestimated. This case study contributes to the growing body of research on the use of pop culture in teaching and learning languages other than English (Werner & Tegge, 2022).

In particular, much of the content used in this course appeared to be already familiar to the students, which helped them engage more readily with unfamiliar aspects of Korean culture and facilitated easier learning of those areas. This underscores the critical role of social media (Zeng & Yung, 2022). As Bahagia et al. (2022) noted, given the widespread popularity of Korean cultural content on platforms like YouTube and streaming services such as Netflix, incorporating K-content into Korean cultural education has the potential to further enhance learning outcomes. The instructional model and case analysis of Korean cultural education presented in this course provide valuable insights for shaping the future of cultural education aimed at foreign students in universities.

However, this case study has some limitations. The survey sample size was relatively small, with only 45 out of 150 students participating. Although the survey link was shared on the K-MOOC platform and email reminders were sent to encourage participation, the online nature of the course likely contributed to the lower-than-expected response rate. Incorporating open-ended questions or conducting small-scale online group interviews could yield more meaningful insights, considering the course's online format.

Finally, one challenge remains in enhancing the effectiveness of cultural courses for foreign learners. While preparing the course, the instructors sought to include a wider range of K-content, such as video materials. However, copyright restrictions limited their ability to use all the resources they intended. This highlights the need for a more flexible system for addressing copyright issues when using content for educational purposes.

Conclusion

With South Korea's economic growth and enhanced cultural influence, the global standing of the Korean language and culture has risen significantly. The continuous expansion of the Korean Wave has sparked a sharp increase in both the Korean language and culture among foreigners. This growing demand for Korean language education as a foreign language has led to the establishment of more programs, not only within Korea but across the globe.

Recently, the role of cultural education in language instruction has been increasingly emphasized, prompting a shift toward enhancing Korean culture education for more effective language learning. In response to this trend, Korean universities have been working to innovate their language education programs for international students. As part of these efforts, our research team developed and implemented a K-MOOC course titled "Learning Korean Culture through K-Content," which utilized various forms of K-content to teach Korean culture. In this study, we introduced a course that explored different aspects of Korean culture through movies, dramas, music, variety shows, and documentaries. A course satisfaction survey was also conducted to assess the impact of using K-content in Korean cultural education. This study confirmed the positive effects of incorporating K-content in Korean language instruction and reinforced the importance of strengthening cultural education as part of language learning.

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